

Twelve Month Report 2020

JIP02-COHESIVE

Responsible Partner: RIVM

Contributing partners: APHA, BfR, IZS-AM,
SVA, WBVR

GENERAL INFORMATION

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12 MONTH REPORT Y3 COHESIVE

1. Summary of the work carried out

As stated earlier, the coming together and extensively discuss issues in a physical meeting is very important for an integrative project such as COHESIVE. In addition to work on the content of the project, the getting to know each other and build trust and respect is key as well. Unfortunately, this was hampered strongly as a result of the COVID-19 epidemic. However, after in first instance delaying in the hope for physical meetings, resilience was shown and the communication of all tasks was switched towards virtual meetings and workshops. Also the reduced capacity within especially public health institutes led to delay of several tasks.

For Task 2.1 the main goal is to develop guidelines for *national* One Health systems or other ways to strengthen human-veterinary-food collaborations, with the aim to improve signalling, risk assessment and response (risk analysis) to zoonoses. A lot of information has been gathered throughout the project, and is currently turned into a guideline. The guideline will be web-based and eventually coupled to the MedVetNet association website in order to be able to maintain the guideline also after OHEJP ends. Within Task 2.3 several pilots are planned in which countries will go through the first steps of the guidelines. Belgium, Portugal, Norway and Italy will take part. In three countries a core group (change agents) has been established and a stakeholder analysis is (partly) performed. However, due to COVID-19 the systems mapping workshops have all been delayed.

For Task 2.2 the goal was to develop an online decision support tool to help the user decide on the most appropriate method to use when tasked with conducting a risk assessment for a specific situation. The tool will direct the user to one of fourteen resources, which include guidance documents, tools and models. The tool is completed as version 1 and it is live, a web address has been circulated to EJP members. The deliverable associated with this task was delivered in Dec 2019, however it has been significantly improved since and work is ongoing to move a copy of it to the EJP website. The tool is designed so that it can be updated as new risk assessment resources emerge and tool improvements are continuing to be made as they are identified through feedback in the project.

Task 3.1: The task focuses on identifying factors that contribute to well-functioning systems or ways to share signals of zoonotic events within and between countries. Interviews of persons working within food safety, public health and veterinary medicine at central, regional or local level were performed in six countries. The thematic analysis of the interview data has been finalized at the national level and a joint thematic analysis is ongoing.

For Task 3.2 a follow-up of the horizon scanning pilot exercise regarding One Health that took place in Nov 2019 has been conducted. The main drivers for One Health were considered to be political and decision making behaviour, people and consumer behaviour, science and innovations, market behaviour, new and re-emerging pathogens or threats and climate change .

For Task 3.3 the aim is to learn from past experiences with respect to zoonotic outbreaks. Hantavirus and Q-fever in the UK were chosen to be retrospectively analyzed. All UK-government publications relating to Hantavirus and Q-fever have been compiled and their data-sources tracked and mapped. A general European-level Q-fever surveillance map has been made in a similar way, using input from consortium members and available online publications. Following an initial systems mapping, with a specific focus on Q-Fever, a number of potential improvements to surveillance in England have been identified and will be highlighted to animal health surveillance colleagues at a planned meeting in Dec.

For Task 3.4, pilot One-Health Early Warning System, the aim is to build on the findings of the previous tasks (i.e. tasks 2.1, 3.1, 3.2) and share low threshold potential signals for pathogens with One-Health impacts across multiple countries within the consortium. Through the initial meeting we can build relationships between countries and start a forum that can continue post-project and is seen as being of value for the long term. . Unfortunately due to the outbreak of highly pathogenic avian influenza across Northern Europe the first meeting has been further postponed until the Early 2021.

For Task 3.5, development of tool for systematic cost-benefit analysis (CBA), the aim was to build on previous experience in the area of CBA to produce a tool and/or method that is applicable to zoonotic pathogens. As CBA can vary due to within country specific conditions that affect both costs and benefits, having a common method attempts to make the CBA comparable across countries. A literature review of CBA methods is underway, with the aim of producing a report focussing on the similarities, differences, strengths and weaknesses of different models and methods. This will incorporate input from other OHEJP members in order to gather CBA experience from across the OHEJP consortium. The systematic review will culminate in a framework for optimizing CBA studies which would help to ensure that future studies are harmonized and directly comparable.

For WP4.1 the aim is to develop a prototype information system at the national level allowing different databases to be interoperable. For this a survey has been conducted in order to gather detailed information on existing databases and information systems for WGS data management and analysis adopted or available among countries. A demo version of the COHESIVE prototype information system (CIS) is made and available for Italy. The feasibility studies in The Netherlands, Italy and Norway are ongoing. Italy feasibility study is almost finished, while the others have some delay.

In WP4.2, the development of the tracing web portal - FoodChain-Lab Web – (FCL Web) advanced further. A revised login procedure and data security documents are currently being developed and the production mode is set up. Also, a JSON-based data exchange format allows for analysing delivery data from a data collection mask developed in a national project in FCL Web.

In WP4.3. the development of shiny app for quantitative risk assessment is completed in the first step. A user-friendly menu structure was implemented for the development of quantitative models. For saving and loading models, the JSON exchange format and the RDA format were developed. The user has the possibility to perform a data fitting with an own data set and simulate models by 1- or 2- dim. Monte-Carlo simulation.

2. Work carried out in the JIP, scientific results and integrative outcomes

1. WP1: Coordination, communication and sustainability

JIP2-WP1-T1: Coordination (M1-M36)

The steering group is meeting online every 5 weeks. In these meetings all tasks are discussed shortly, including (possible) problems. Also general tasks are discussed and decided upon, such as annual meetings and reports. There have been several contacts with EFSA, mainly concerning WP4, but also regular video-conferences are organized between the contact persons of EFSA and the coordinator of COHESIVE. Unfortunately, ECDC didn't have a contact person available for COHESIVE, but a new person will be appointed. ORION and NOVA are other OHEJP projects to which COHESIVE closely relates. ORION, NOVA and COHESIVE are working together at a glossary including terms used within the different projects. A publication is in preparation.

JIP2-WP1-T2: Communication/dissemination (M1-M36)

Since in 2019 two general (annual) meetings were organized, the annual meeting that was planned in March 2020, was postponed. Due to many planned conferences (i.e. World One Health Conference, ASM OHEJP, IAFP European Symposium on Food Safety Food) in Spring it was postponed to Autumn. Due to COVID-19 we transformed the annual meeting into a virtual one, which took place on November 24th and 26th. The annual meeting was open to all OHEJP members and stakeholders. Indeed members from other projects were present as well as EFSA, ECDC and FAO. EFSA also gave a presentation. As a spin-off, we had organized a workshop on systems thinking as a satellite workshop before the ASM in Prague. However, this could not go through. Also the workshop during the IAFP European Symposium on Food Safety conference was cancelled. The outbreak preparedness workshop for PhD students, which was cancelled only a few days in advance due to the large COVID-19 outbreak, eventually took place as a virtual event. This is a very important topic which fits very well within the key issues COHESIVE wants to address (be prepared in a One Health fashion for emerging zoonoses) and which is more than ever relevant. There are also regular meetings with project leaders from all integrative projects, led by the OHEJP WP4 leader. Other dissemination activities that did take place, related to the other work packages, are indicated below.

2. WP2. Integrated risk-analysis at the national level

JIP2-WP2-T1: Development of guidelines for national One Health structures (M1-M26)

The main goal of this task is the development of guidelines in order to support countries to set up/strengthen the collaboration between the human-vet-food domains with respect to signaling, risk assessment, response and control of zoonoses. During the general meeting in Rome in November 2019 it was decided to disseminate the guidelines as a website. This would facilitate easy searching of dedicated information, based on the needs of the user. An outline of the website has been made. The webdesigner currently is transferring our wishes into a layout. Already a lot of information has been gathered during the workshops in 2018 and 2019. This information is in the process of being transferred into useful information for the users of the website. In the workshops also information has been gathered on barriers that can be faced when trying to organize risk analysis of zoonoses in a One Health fashion. Important barriers such as obtaining political will and building trust are deepened by performing dedicated interviews. The interviews are analysed and the results will be translated into tips and tricks in the guidelines to support countries with these kind of barriers. After the OHEJP ends, the guideline-website will be transferred to the MedVetNet Association (MVNA) and linked to their website, to secure long term sustainability.

There is regular contact with the FAO with respect to the Tripartite Zoonoses Guide (TZG) of OIE, WHO and FAO, specifically in relation to the SISOT work group, and now also contacts are made with the WHO in relation to the governance part of the TZG.

It became clear in the first 2 years, that physical workshops are the best way to co-create the guidelines. Because the results from a workshop are input for the next and good preparation is key to a successful meeting, the workshops can't be too close together. Unfortunately, due to COVID-19 no physical workshop has taken place this year. After postponing workshops a couple of times, at a certain moment we had to conclude that physical meetings were no longer an option in 2020. Therefore, we started organizing virtual workshops. Learning by doing, it turned out that also now good preparation was essential. The preparation is very labor-intensive and even though the participants are engaged, the output is limited compared to physical meetings. Partly, because the assignments are more complicated to perform online and partly because people are only dedicated for a short period of time (2hours) instead of i.e. 2 days. This did result in quite a delay of this task. Another additional factor for the delay is the fact that key personell, especially in public health organisations were occupied in COVID-19 activities and therefore not available for COHESIVE activities. The timeline until June 2021 is very tight for this task. Although we will be able to deliver a website with guidelines by that time, the quality most likely will be affected by the COVID-19 crisis.

Figure 1: Draft picture illustrating the stepping stones for the implementation process which will be included in the website 'One Health: Setting up a risk analysis system for zoonoses.'

JIP2-WP2-T2: Development of structured decision making (M1-M24)

The deliverable for this task was delivered during 2019, this produced a prototype tool of a decision tree framework to help the user decide on the most appropriate method to use when tasked with conducting a risk assessment for a specific situation. The tool has been significantly improved since the delivery in 2019. The tool is designed so that it can be updated as new risk assessment resources emerge. The tool will direct the user to one of fourteen resources, which include guidance documents, tools and models. The tool, now run in a javascript-enabled browser, has supporting text outlining purpose and caveats, and has adopted EJP colours. It references the grant agreement in a footer, and also provides links to the OHEJP homepage and EJP homepage. No further dissemination activities have been done, however a short communication to accompany the tool has been drafted. Active development of the tool is nearing completion and we are currently seeking web-space to host the tool, aiming to do so through collaboration within the consortium and wider EJP. Continuing updates to the contents of the tool are carried out through 'show and tell' sessions at consortium meetings.

JIP2-WP2-T3: Knowledge transfer and dissemination (M25-M35)

Different dissemination activities of WP2 have taken place during the OHEJP ASM; an oral presentation and a poster both related to the development of the guideline in WP2.1. Also an oral presentation on the guidelines during the World One Health Conference was given.

An important element of this workpackage is the actual use of the guidelines developed in WP2.1. The guidelines focus on implementation and operationalization. The idea is to have pilots in several European countries to start with implementing or strengthening the collaboration between the human-veterinary-food domain in the area of signaling, risk assessment, response and control of zoonoses. By doing that during the project experiences within the pilots could feed back to further improve the guidelines. However, due to COVID-19 the progression which was on scheme was stopped abruptly. The pilot countries are Norway, Portugal, Italy and Belgium. After setting the goal and performance of a stakeholder analysis Belgium was ready for step 3, the systems mapping workshop. This workshop should have taken place on March 27, but was cancelled a few days in advance. After trying to postpone to June, the new aim was to have it in October. However, due to the changing COVID-19 situation in Belgium it turned out not to be possible after all and it is further delayed. Also, the other pilots were strongly hampered by the COVID-19 crisis. However, Norway managed to make a draft systems map and performed a stakeholder analysis. Italy and Portugal have done the first part of the stakeholder analysis online. Since the prospects are not very positive and travel seems not to be feasible at a short term, we decided to try to organize a systems mapping workshop in which the participants are physically present as well as the local moderators, but the lead will be done virtually from Swiss. The first country who will try this approach is Norway, most likely followed by Belgium. Hopefully, we will manage to perform the first 3 steps (setting goal, stakeholder analysis and systems mapping) in all four pilot countries. These experiences will be used to improve the guidelines. Unfortunately, hardly any time will be left for the following steps, reducing the impact of these show cases for other countries.

3. WP3: Towards an EU zoonoses structure

JIP2-WP3-T1: Explore current ways for exchanging signals between countries and cross disciplines – pathway analysis (M1-M24)

The task focuses on identifying factors that contribute to well-functioning systems or ways to share signals of zoonotic events within and between countries. During a workshop in Uppsala in 2019 the focus of the task was set to identify different factors that contribute to well-functioning systems or ways to share signals as well as factors that prevent sharing of signals, both within and between countries, focusing on the persons in the systems rather than the technical or organizational solutions. In depth semi-structured interviews were considered to capture more in-depth information than a written questionnaire. Interviews of persons working within food safety, public health and veterinary medicine at central, regional or local level were performed in six countries. COVID-19 has affected some of the interviews.

The first round of national data analysis has been completed although COVID-19 has delayed the analysis. Performing the joint thematic analysis was planned as an activity done in physical meeting, but was turned into a virtual one. In general, the participating countries have experienced that they through the interviews have received new information which is relevant when understanding signal sharing. Several themes identified were common for the participating countries, and some of the findings were even surprisingly similar between countries. One theme that was mentioned by a majority of the participants was the importance of knowing someone in person, which was described as a prerequisite for informal contacts which are often used for signal sharing. Other themes were: 1) the need for formal structures for sharing signals (e.g. legislation, clear routines) which was not in contrast to the personal contacts – both are needed, 2) further need for understanding of the mandates of persons working in different sectors, 3) prioritization can be affected by prior knowledge and experience, 4) the technical (IT) systems can be beneficial but several examples were given of outdated systems, parallel systems or systems not accessible between sectors, 5) legal restrictions for sharing data was described as a hinder for signal sharing, 6) concern or fear of overreaction by the recipient of the signal and concern or fear for leakage of the information were concerns raised in relation to signal sharing.

Based on the findings, the following preliminary recommendations have been developed: 1) Acknowledge the importance of personal contacts and ensure that there are occasions when people can see each other (eg regular meetings) or collaborate to learn to know each other. 2) Make sure there

are structures in place, and understanding for each other's roles and mandates. 3) Strive for well-functioning cross-sectional technical systems, make it possible to share and access data.

Two presentations were given at the OHEJP annual conference in Prague, one oral presenting the results from the Italian part of the study, and one poster describing the whole project. The work drafting the manuscript has continued. Further, another project, close to Task 3.1, was presented for the DG Santé in January 2020 while they performed an audit in Sweden on "Early detection and notification systems in place for emerging animal diseases". The representatives from DG Santé were very interested in the study and in the preliminary findings presented. **The results from 3.1 have also been presented for working groups within the OHEJP-project Matrix.**

JIP2-WP3-T2: Horizon Scanning Pilot Exercise (M1-M24)

The pilot horizon scanning exercise that took place in November 2019 was based on an assembly of information sources and an assembly of analysis teams with assigned topics. Within task 3.2 a horizon scanning team composed of experts within public health, animal health, food safety has been established. To explore the potential application of such a technique, the pilot exercise first identified more than 30 potential One Health issues. From these a summary of six drivers were identified to have a key impact in the next coming years: political and decision making behaviour, people and consumer behaviour, science and innovations, market behaviour, new and re-emerging pathogens or threats and climate change. The conducted pilot horizon scanning exercise showed to be useful but needs to be further developed for foresight applications related to One Health in Europe. The One Health pilot horizon scanning exercise took place (Nov 2019) prior to the covid-19 pandemic. Even though the foresight was focused on One Health the exercise identified many issues that have been of relevance during the last months. The task leader participated in a horizon scanning exercise organised by the WHO, using similar methodology. A scientific report on the horizon scanning exercise is in progress. The results were presented in a poster at the One Health EJP Annual Scientific Meeting in May 2020.

JIP2-WP3-T3: Retrospective systems analysis of detection of outbreaks (M6-M30)

The aim of this task is to learn from past experiences with respect to zoonotic outbreaks. Hantavirus and Q-fever in the UK were chosen to be retrospectively analyzed. All UK-government publications relating to Hantavirus and Q-fever have been compiled and their data-sources tracked and mapped. After this, all data gathered from the November 2019 workshop has been used to map One-Health surveillance structures for Q-fever into a general European map from consortium partners. Cross-comparing these has identified the 'common core' of components that are present in all those countries. Due to COVID-19 work on this component paused in mid-March but has since resumed. Collaboration with participants in refining, adding detail and finalising the One Health structures in each country is still required, and is significantly delayed by COVID-19. In tandem, a map of Q-fever surveillance protocols in the UK veterinary sector has been made to identify local strengths and weaknesses. We hope to expand this across public health and food safety in the UK.

JIP2-WP3-T4: Pilot One-Health Early Warning System (M25-M36)

The core feature of this pilot was originally envisaged to start with a face to face meeting with One-Health professionals across the COHESIVE project. Due to COVID-19 it is unlikely that such a meeting can take place. We have amended the plans to convert this to an online format and are currently focused on identifying One Health representatives in institutes involved in COHESIVE. Aims, objectives and terms of reference will be drafted for the meetings and development of the documents can be carried out online.

There will be additional challenges to developing such a group only online as trust plays a significant part in open sharing of information and ideas, this may slow the effective development of such a group and will require innovative approaches. Unfortunately due to the ongoing highly pathogenic avian influenza outbreak across Northern Europe the online meeting had to be postponed to early 2021.

limited availability of animal health colleagues. However the network already formed through the COHESIVE project has been collaborating individually around sharing, country specific, risk assessments on HPAI H5N8.

JIP2-WP3-T5: Development of a tool for systematic cost-benefit analysis (CBA) (M25-36)

Due to COVID-19 work on this task has not progressed as much as originally planned as key staff members have been redirected to COVID-19 related activities. An email was circulated to the whole COHESIVE project seeking active contributions to the task. A number of positive responses were received. An abstract for a poster was accepted to the EJP ASM also looking to recruit more members to the project however the revised online format of the meeting made this less effective than hoped. Current work is focused on performing a systematic review of cost-benefit analysis studies within the foodborne zoonosis remit. This will incorporate input from other OHEJP members in order to gather CBA experience from across the OHEJP consortium. The systematic review will culminate in a framework for optimizing CBA studies. Work on the literature review is continuing and preliminary results were discussed at the recent COHESIVE annual meeting. The discussion session highlighted a number of areas where the literature search terms could be improved.

4. WP4: Data platform to facilitate risk-analysis and outbreak control

JIP2-WP4-T1: Molecular typing data and metadata – database creation

The feasibility studies on the three Member States (The Netherlands, Italy, Norway) are ongoing. Three prototypes information systems (cis-holland, cis-italy, cis-norway) are online and have been filled with information provided by the involved member states. RIVM and WBVR of The Netherlands have provided details of their coding systems. They are currently under the harmonization phase. In particular, RIVM has produced the coding systems for HEV but not yet for Listeria. NVI has not produced any coding system for Listeria yet. Both delays are somehow related to COVID-19 pandemic. ISS and NRL are conducting a sharing exercise of WGS data and metadata of *Listeria* and STEC using federated information systems. The architecture has been presented at COHESIVE annual meeting. The coding systems have been harmonized. The bioinformatics analysis harmonization is on going.

JIP2-WP4-T1-ST5: Filling of DBs (M15-M26)

- In the new T4.1 description, the sub-task title is “*Linking of the national databases with the COHESIVE prototype information system and the epidemiological analysis tools*”.
- During the General Meeting on November 2019 in Rome, it was decided to start the activity of integration among the three information systems of the WP4. A telco was planned for the beginning of 2020 followed by face-to-face meeting. The activity has been affected by COVID-19 crisis. The new plan is to finish the activity by the early months of 2021.

JIP2-WP4-T1-ST6: Design and implementation of pipelines (M21-M32)

- In the new T4.1 description, the sub-task title is “*Study of available pipelines*”.
- We are connected with the EJP ORION project, which has a WP specifically dedicated to this activity.
- The activity has been affected by delay of ORION deliverables due to COVID-19 crisis. So far, the deliverable produced by ORION do not describe the details of tools to be used in the pipelines. A new meeting is foreseen with NVI for clarifications.

JIP2-WP4-T2: Development of a platform-independent tracing framework

JIP2-WP4-T2-ST2 (M1-M32)

In subtask 2, several modules for data collection, cleaning, visualisation and reporting – in part developed in the framework of other projects - will be unified in one platform – the FoodChain

Lab web application (FCL Web):

- A data collection module
- An interactive analysis module
- A WGS-data integration module
- A reporting module
- A synchronization module with the desktop version of FoodChain-Lab (FCL)

The overall status and progress of the whole FCL project can be inspected at <https://foodrisklabs.bfr.bund.de/foodchain-lab>. The specific status and new software versions of the FCL Web are deployed automatically to a test server where new features of the tool can be seen live. Since November 2020, FCL Web is in production mode which accessible at <https://fcl-portal.bfr.berlin>. A revised login procedure including obtaining the user's consent to gather personal data as well as data security documents was developed. In addition, a JSON-based data exchange format allows for visualising and analysing delivery data obtained from a data collection mask developed in a national project in FCL Web. In 2020 FCL Web became part of the SISOT tool box.

JIP02-WP4-T2-ST3 (M13-M32)

In several presentations on FoodChain-Lab the audience highlighted the importance for integration of WGS data into tracing network visualisations. In addition to the work performed in 2018 and 2019, an interface to the COHESIVE Information System, the whole genome sequencing database mentioned in JIP-WP4-T1 is planned and work will be intensified in the upcoming weeks. This subtask will not be finished as planned until M32 and is prolonged until M40.

JIP2-WP4-T3: Development of a platform-independent risk modeling framework

JIP2-WP4-T3-ST1: Requirement analysis (M1-M9)

Typical components have been identified that support quantitative microbiological risk assessment, advanced simulation techniques, documentation and extended usability. Selection of minimal models for testing and development is completed. The prioritization of building blocks for implementation in web application of risk is finished.

JIP2-WP4-T3-ST2 Implementation (M10-M30)

Various minimal models from the literature and from project partners were tested and defined. Risk questions and scenarios as well as quantitative risk models were provided by partners in COHESIVE and other EJP projects. As part of the implementation of standards, we were also provided with data sets and use-cases in cooperation with the FLI. Currently, also the search of models and data suitable as case study (ideally with input from project partners) is ongoing. Due to the corona pandemic we have a delay of 3 months. Furthermore, in cooperation with project partners we have prioritized different building blocks. For the web application of risk we developed various mocks to define the workflow and the individual steps of the user interface in R shiny.

In the first step we have successfully implemented the one-dimensional Monte-Carlo simulation in our web application. The Prototype of "quantitative Riskanalysis" was developed and is finished. With "quantitative Riskanalysis" different risk models can now be implemented and calculated. The implementation of further statistical methods for quantitative risk assessment is also finished with the support of an external software company.

With our new Shiny app for probabilistic analysis, users can now create and calculate their own mathematical model. The special features of this tool are the data fitting with user-specific data, the evaluation of uncertainties e.g. model uncertainty, scenario uncertainty and item uncertainty as well as a complete documentation of the model which contributes to transparency and reusability of models.

With our Shiny R App "Rrisk" the user now has the possibility to run one and two dimensional Monte-Carlo simulations via a user friendly interface and to view and document the results.

JIP2-WP4-T4: Dissemination

Although dissemination duties of WP4 achievements start only from M25, a lot of dissemination work for FCL and the tracing portal that was set up in COHESIVE was done in the framework of other projects in the years 2018 and 2019 (workshops and presentations on FCL, meetings with stakeholders). In the framework of COHESIVE annual meetings, presentations and workshops for WP4 tools were conducted for the COHESIVE community.

WP4 activities were presented at the 2020 OHEJP Annual Scientific Meeting in an online format (presentation on COHESIVE Information System, poster on FoodChain-Lab Web). In 2021 a joint interactive workshop on WP4 tools and how they interact is envisioned as a satellite event for the COHESIVE final meeting which is open for the COHESIVE community and other interested users. Furthermore, FCL Web will be presented in an interactive virtual event and e learning course in the framework of the One Health EJP Continuing Professional Development module in 2021 (<https://onehealthejp.eu/cpd-2021/>). In 2020 FCL Web became part of the SISOT tool box.

Progress of the project: milestones and deliverables

Deliverables

JIP code	Project deliverable number (Original number, if different from the actual one)	Deliverable name (Original name, if different from the actual one)	Delivery date from AWP 2020	Date delivered on Project Group website	If deliverable not submitted: Forecast delivery date	Is this delay due to COVID-19?	Comments (Please mention: public or confidential, the Zenodo reference and other comments)	Proposed category* (1 to 8) (several categories may be applicable)
COHESIVE	D-JIP2-1.5	Annual meeting	26	26-11-2020			Since we have had a second meeting with the whole consortium in November 2019, this annual meeting was already postponed to Autumn 2020. Due to COVID-19 we cancelled the physical meeting and changed it into an online annual meeting	4,8
COHESIVE	D- JIP2-1.6	Annual report	28	14-01-2020				4,8
COHESIVE	D- JIP2-1.7	Closing symposium	36		42		An extension of 6M months has been granted. Therefore, this closing symposium will be postponed to month 42	4,8
COHESIVE	D- JIP2-1.8	Annual report	36	21-12-2020				4,8
COHESIVE	D- JIP2-2.5	Development of common procedures and tools	26		38		Very dependent on physical meetings. Appeared to difficult to arrange frequently and has also been hampered very much by the COVID-19 crisis	8
COHESIVE	D- JIP2-2.6	Knowledge transfer and dissemination	34		42		Very much dependent on physical workshops. This has been extremely hampered by the COVID-19 crisis	8
COHESIVE	D- JIP2-3.3	Pathway analysis of exchanging signals	10	21-12-2020			This deliverable was further delayed due to COVID-19. The deliverable is a report on the preliminary results as well as recommendations based on the study has	8

							been finalised. Further joint thematic analysis over countries is still ongoing and a manuscript is being drafted.	
COHESIVE	D- JIP2-3.5	System analysis of detection of outbreaks	24		42		This deliverable had already been extended. Draft of UK systems map completed Dec-2019. Work currently paused due to COVID-19 but has been restarted	8
COHESIVE	D- JIP2-3.6	Knowledge transfer and dissemination	34		42		Delayed as transfer and dissemination will wait until completion of all deliverables. Due to COVID-19 several deliverables have been delayed.	8
COHESIVE	D- JIP2-3.7	Drivers of change in One Health– a horizon scanning exercise (new deliverable)	30	31-12-2020			New deliverable, not listed in the proposal. A horizon scanning exercise was done at the general meeting in November 2019. Material compiled within WP3.2 (including the exercise) will be compiled.	2,8
COHESIVE	D- JIP2-3.8	Tool for systematic cost-benefit analysis	36		40		New deliverable, not listed in the proposal. Started on collating the results of literature review between AGES and APHA, however work is paused due to COVID-19	2,8
COHESIVE	D- JIP2-4.1.3	Databases containing the country data	26	30-03-2020			The three prototypes information systems (cis-holland, cis-italy, cis-norway) have been filled with information provided by the involved member states. Details are on the deliverable uploaded to the EJP platform end of March 2020.	4
COHESIVE	D- JIP2-4.1.4	Description of the pipelines implemented to feed the analysis tools with the data stored in the three databases of this project	32		40		Partial information is gathered from involved member states. Pipelines specification will be taken from an ORION deliverable specifically dedicated to this activity. Pipelines integration will start just after ORION deliverable publication. Information was expected to be shared and harmonized among the others softwares from WP4. Covid crisis delayed this point.	4

COHESIVE	D- JIP2-4.2.2	FoodChain-Lab with integrated network analysis module as a web-service browser-ready, open source and implemented in the BfR cloud Integration and analysis of epi-	32	31.08.2020			FCL Web is already accessible at https://fcl-portal.bfr.berlin .	4,8
COHESIVE	D- JIP2-4.2.3							

Milestones

JIP Code	Milestone number	Milestone name	Delivery date from AWP 2020	Achieved (Yes/No)	If not achieved: Forecast achievement date	Comments
COHESIVE	M-AI2.COHESIVE.1.3	Annual report	28	Yes		
COHESIVE	M-AI2.COHESIVE.1.4	Closing symposium	36		42	An extension of 6M months has been granted. Therefore, this end symposium will be postponed to month 42
COHESIVE	M-AI2.COHESIVE.1.5	Annual report	36	Yes		
COHESIVE	M-AI2.COHESIVE.2.2	Development of common procedures and tools	26	No	38	Very dependent on physical meetings. Appeared difficult to arrange frequently and has also been hampered by the COVID-19 crisis
COHESIVE	M-AI2.COHESIVE.2.3	Knowledge transfer and dissemination	34		40	Very much dependent on physical workshops. This has been extremely hampered by the COVID-19 crisis
COHESIVE	M-AI2.COHESIVE.3.1	Development of common procedures and tools for horizon scanning	26	Yes		A literature review and a report on the workshop and horizon scanning exercise has been finalised.
COHESIVE	M-AI2.COHESIVE.3.2	Pathway and system analysis of signal exchange and outbreak detection	24	Yes		A report on task 3.1 is finalised. The task was delayed partly due to COVID-19.
COHESIVE	M-AI2.COHESIVE.3.3	Local dissemination	34		42	The local pilots are very much delayed due to COVID-19

COHESIVE	M-A2.COHESIVE.4.7	Databases containing the country data	26	Yes		The three prototypes information systems (cis-holland, cis-italy, cis-norway) have been filled with information provided by the involved member states. Details are on the deliverable uploaded to the EJP platform end of March 2020.
COHESIVE	M-A2. COHESIVE.4.8	Prototype for risk modeling framework ready	30	Yes		Prototype “quantitative riskanalysis” for risk modelling frame is available on github. ChristinWallstab/rrisk-maibornwolff (github.com)
COHESIVE	M-A2.COHESIVE.4.9	Availability of the pipelines from the databases to the analysis tools	32		40	Partial information is gathered from involved member states. Pipelines specification will be taken from an ORION deliverable specifically dedicated to this activity. Pipelines integration will start just after ORION deliverable publication. Information was expected to be shared and harmonized among the others softwares from WP4. Covid crisis delayed this point.
COHESIVE	M-A2. COHESIVE.4.10	Analysis of epi-data into tracing framework enclosed	34		40	Some epi-data (case information, sample data) already integrated into FCL Web. However, for this milestone i.e. the WGS data to be integrated and analysed in FCL Web, will be delayed due to travel restrictions and shortage of staff due to COVID-19 associated issues
COHESIVE	M-A2. COHESIVE.4.11	Final release of risk modeling framework	34		40	Final release of risk modeling framework is going, the shiny app is a is in a producible state. Docker pipeline is under development.

2. Publications and additional outputs

Additional output

WP2 Presentations at the OHEJP annual meeting in Prague 27-29 May, 2020

COHESIVE: Development of implementation guidelines to support countries with early warning, response and control of (emerging) zoonoses in a One Health fashion

COHESIVE: Understanding the needs for European implementation guidelines for a One Health Risk Analysis System for zoonoses

Ines

WP3 Presentations at the OHEJP annual meeting in Prague

WP3 Presentations at the OHEJP annual meeting in Prague 27-29 May, 2020

Factors affecting signals sharing of zoonotic events: a qualitative exploratory study in Italy

To share or not to share - the exchange of signals of zoonotic events within and between countries in Europe

Horizon scanning pilot exercise regarding One Health

WP4 Presentations at the OHEJP annual meeting in Prague

cgDIST: a new methodology to inferring phylogeny

The COHESIVE Information System: a cross EJP projects example

The FoodChain-Lab Web application – an integrative tracing tool to analyse complex global food supply chains in foodborne crises

Abstracts can be accessed from the proceedings of the 2nd Annual Scientific Meeting of the One Health European Joint Programme on Foodborne Zoonoses, Antimicrobial Resistance and Emerging Threats. <https://onehealthjep.eu/wp-content/uploads/2018/12/D3.12-OHEJP-ASM-2020-Abstract-book.pdf>

WP2 Presentations at the World One Health Conference in Edinburgh 30 Oct - 3 November 2020

COHESIVE: Development of implementation guidelines to support countries with early warning, response and control of (emerging) zoonoses in a One Health fashion

Frank Koenen, Sandra Cavaco Gonçalves, Solveig Jore, Charlotte Cook, Elina Lahti, Karin Nyberg, Malin Jonsson, Frits Vlaanderen, Ines Mogami, Mathilde Uiterwijk, Gaia Scavia, Kitty Maassen (presenting author)

:
European guidelines for a One Health Risk Analysis System for zoonotic diseases: a needs assessment using implementation theory

3. On-going and planned collaborations with national or European projects or networks

FAO WHO

NOVA ORION

In WP4.2 there is a close collaboration with **EFSA** with focus on tracing solutions in the framework of an EFSA-BfR Framework Partnership Agreement. Also, FCL was part of joint **ECDC-EFSA** crisis trainings. There are also links to the EJP **NOVA** project in which a module for analysis of sales data should be integrated into FCL On the national level, FCL is involved in a project with the German federal state North-Rhine Westphalia on developing a data entry mask for supply chain data. Several modules of the tracing portal were developed in the framework of these projects and the aim of COHESIVE is to unify all of them under one umbrella – the FCL tracing portal. In October 2020 in the framework of a **MedVetNet** short term mission, a guest scientist from Istituto Superiore di Sanità in Italy who is also involved in NOVA WP2 and COHESIVE WP3 visited BfR to learn more about tracing and FCL as well as FCL Web. In 2020 FCL Web became part of the SISOT tool box initiated by **OIE, WHO and FAO**. Within task 3.1 there are links to a task within NOVA on early detection and notification of transmissible animal diseases.

In WP4.1 there is a close collaboration with ORION to integrate ontologies on the prototype COHESIVE Information system (CIS). The project EJP **BeOne** is interested to work on top of this result.

Additional contacts are made with **Matrix** and **Televir**. The two EJP projects are evaluating to build their activities upon results from the Cohesive information system.

4. Data Management Plan

The DMP of COHESIVE can be found on the OHEJP website in the DMP group. At the end of the project all data are fulfilling the FAIR principle. These include models of which also documentation and codes fulfill the FAIR principle. In 2021 the DMP will be checked for missing information and action will start to make sure the DMP is complete by the end of the project.

5. Follow-up of the recommendations and comments in previous review(s) by the Ethics Advisors

Requirements of Ethical Reviewers, January 2018	Project's measures and actions taken at the end of 2018	Comments of Ethics Advisors, January 2019	Comments Project Leaders, end of 2019	Comments of Ethics Advisors, January 2020	Comments Project Leaders, mid-2020	Comments of Ethics Advisors, November 2020
n.a.	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.

6. List of critical risks

Description of risk	Yes/No
Loss of key-persons (staff and / or leaders)	Yes
Delay in work plan execution	Yes
Conflicts within the consortium	No
Lack of commitment of partners	Yes
Delay in duties, tasks or reporting	Yes
Poor intra-project relationship	No
Potential entry/exit of partners	Yes
Other risks (please describe)	COVID

Additional information

Some indicated risks already led to delays (see previous reports). The major current problem is COVID-19. This leads to delay in work plan execution as well as to delay in duties, tasks and reporting. This was already the case, before COVID-19. The combination might lead to not making all deliverables or with lower quality than expected. The main reasons are the reduced availability of (key-)personell and travel restrictions

Several modules to be integrated into the tracing portal are developed in the framework of other projects. However, if such a project fails to develop a usable module, the respective module cannot be integrated into the COHESIVE tracing portal

